

Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia in Hospital General De Playa Del Carmen: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

The Bochdalek hernia results from the passage of abdominal contents into the thorax through the posterolateral diaphragmatic foramen, predominantly affecting the left side. We present the case of a term female neonate (39.6 weeks) with a prenatal diagnosis of probable duodenal atresia. At birth, a left-sided congenital diaphragmatic hernia was identified, leading to intestinal loop reduction and diaphragmatic plasty. The patient received multidisciplinary management and was discharged following improvement. Congenital diaphragmatic hernia can be diagnosed prenatally, with over 50% of cases identified between 16–24 weeks of gestation via ultrasonography. Early detection and timely surgical intervention are critical for improving prognosis and reducing complications in these patients.

KEYWORDS: neonate; congenital diaphragmatic hernia; Bochdalek; surgery; intestinal loop reduction; diaphragmatic plasty

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INTRODUCTION

Congenital diaphragmatic hernia (CDH) is a developmental defect characterized by incomplete diaphragm formation, allowing abdominal organs to herniate into the thoracic cavity. This anomaly often leads to pulmonary hypoplasia and persistent pulmonary hypertension (PPH), the primary causes of neonatal morbidity and mortality associated with CDH [1]. Diaphragm development occurs between 4–12 weeks of gestation, a critical period for embryological anomalies. The Bochdalek hernia, located posterolaterally, accounts for 70–75% of cases, predominantly on the left side (85%). In contrast, Morgagni hernias (anterior) and central hernias are less common, representing 2–28% of cases [2].

Depending on the defect's size, organs such as the stomach, spleen, liver, and small intestine may shift into the thoracic cavity, impairing normal lung development. The incidence of CDH is estimated at 1 in 3,000–5,000 live births, with post-diagnosis survival exceeding 60%, depending on defect severity and available medical interventions [3, 4]. Prenatal diagnosis is essential for optimizing perinatal management. Prenatal ultrasound detects CDH by identifying abdominal organs in the thoracic cavity and impaired lung development. Fetal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) complements diagnosis by assessing lung volume and associated anomalies, crucial for determining neonatal prognosis.

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The Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia Study Group (CDHSG) classification of defect size aids in predicting clinical outcomes. Larger defects are associated with increased risks of respiratory failure, chronic lung disease, and the need for extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO).

Adequate prenatal care enables early CDH detection, facilitating referral to specialized centers for comprehensive, multidisciplinary management, thereby improving survival and reducing complications.

This report aims to present a clinical case of CDH diagnosed and treated at Hospital General of Playa del Carmen, highlighting key aspects of prenatal detection, perioperative management, and clinical outcomes. It emphasizes the importance of early identification and multidisciplinary care in a second-level hospital to optimize neonatal prognosis.

CASE REPORT

We present a female newborn, born to a 24-year-old mother with adequate prenatal care (six visits from the first trimester), treated for a urinary tract infection in the third trimester with an unspecified medication. A pelvic ultrasound at 15 weeks (07.09.2022) indicated probable dextrocardia and a double-bubble sign, suggesting duodenal atresia. Delivery

was performed via cesarean section due to fetal bradycardia (95 bpm).

On 08.09.2022, a non-vigorous female neonate was received with clear amniotic fluid, generalized cyanosis, poor respiratory effort, and a heart rate <100 bpm. One cycle of positive pressure ventilation (PPV) was provided, with adequate response. Supplemental oxygen was continued via free flow, but cyanosis persisted upon withdrawal. Patent choanae, esophagus, and anus were confirmed, and the umbilical cord (two arteries, one vein) was clamped and cut without bleeding. APGAR scores were 4/7, Silverman-Anderson 3/4, with nasal flaring, intercostal retractions, expiratory grunting, and thoracoabdominal dissociation. Capurro assessment indicated 37 weeks' gestation. Somatometry: weight 2,560 g, length 48 cm, head circumference 31 cm, thoracic circumference 31 cm, abdominal circumference 29 cm, subcostal circumference 21 cm, foot length 7.5 cm. The neonate was placed in an incubator with supplemental oxygen via a head hood at 10 liters per minute. Physical examination revealed a bulging left hemithorax, rhythmic heart sounds of adequate intensity in the right hemithorax, vesicular murmur present in the right hemithorax but absent in the left, with no added sounds. The abdomen was soft, without palpable masses or organomegaly, and peristaltic sounds were absent.

Figure 1.

Due to severe respiratory distress, advanced airway management was performed with endotracheal intubation (3 Fr tube, fixed at 9 cm from the labial commissure), connected to mechanical ventilation (PIP 16, PEEP 5, rate 40, FiO₂ 30%), achieving SpO₂ >90%. Arterial blood gas analysis showed pH 7.32, PCO₂ 34, PO₂ 16.40, HCO₃ 18.70, base excess -8.6, lactate 2.40. A chest X-ray was performed upon admission to neonatal intensive care (Figure 1).

CDH was confirmed, and pediatric cardiology was consulted. An echocardiogram on 09.09.2022 revealed a structurally normal heart, patent ductus arteriosus (4.3 x 6.0 x 4.9 mm,

left-to-right shunt, gradient 21 mmHg), preserved ventricular function, and suprasystemic right ventricular systolic pressure. With no surgical contraindications, pediatric surgery evaluated the patient, noting bilateral thoracic ventilation despite peristaltic sounds in the left hemithorax, suggesting mild left lung hypoplasia and a better prognosis. The globular abdominal appearance indicated a large defect allowing free passage of intestinal loops. Given stable hemodynamics, intestinal loop reduction and diaphragmatic plasty were scheduled to promote lung development and reduce pulmonary hypertension risk.

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Surgery was performed on 09.09.2022 via open laparotomy with a supraumbilical midline incision. A 5 cm posterolateral left hemidiaphragmatic defect was identified, containing approximately 30% of the small intestine and ascending colon without vascular compromise. The intestinal loops were reduced without complications. Primary closure was

performed using 4-0 Prolene sutures, with simple stitches directed toward the diaphragmatic tendon to minimize tearing risk. No immediate recurrence was observed, and the defect was classified as a Bochdalek hernia. An intraoperative chest X-ray confirmed successful closure and left lung re-expansion (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

Post-surgery, the patient was admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit with hypothermia, non-perfusing mean arterial pressure, and bradycardia, requiring inotropic support with dopamine and dobutamine (10 mcg/kg/min each), achieving adequate blood pressure and heart rate. Milrinone was initiated at maintenance dose. Mechanical ventilation continued in assist-control mode (PIP 20, PEEP 5, rate 50, FiO₂ 60%), maintaining adequate respiratory pattern and SpO₂ >95%. Antimicrobial coverage with ampicillin and amikacin was started after blood culture collection, along with sedation using midazolam and fentanyl.

On 13.09.2022 personally, pediatric cardiology reassessed the patient post-surgery, noting normal hemodynamics, reduced pulmonary pressure, and left ventricular opening. A 3 x 3 mm

mid-trabecular ventricular septal defect (VSD) was identified (right-to-left shunt, systolic gradient 9 mmHg), likely obscured pre-surgery by intestinal compression. The VSD was small relative to body surface area, with potential for spontaneous closure. The patent ductus arteriosus persisted (left-to-right shunt, systolic gradient 9 mmHg), prompting pharmacological closure and loop diuretic (0.5 mg/kg/dose every 8 hours). Ventricular function remained preserved, with right ventricular systolic pressure at 53 mmHg.

On 13.09.2022, a left pleural effusion was detected (Figure 3), managed with an endopleural tube, draining 40 ml of serohemorrhagic fluid. The tube was removed after nine days, with no radiographic evidence of effusion (Figure 4).

Figure 3.

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High ventilatory parameters were required, with progressive titration until programmed withdrawal of mechanical ventilation on 27.09.2022. The patient received head hood oxygen for three days and free-flow oxygen for one day, with supplemental oxygen discontinued on 01.10.2022, maintaining SpO₂ >95% without respiratory distress.

Empirical antibiotics (ampicillin and amikacin) were stopped after five days due to slow response, replaced with cefotaxime and vancomycin for 14 days. A central blood culture

(08.09.2022) showed no bacterial growth, but a pleural fluid culture (13.09.2022) grew vancomycin-sensitive *S. epidermidis*, supporting continued antibiotic therapy. Low cardiac output post-surgery required dopamine for seven days, dobutamine for 12 days, and norepinephrine for three days.

The patient exhibited favorable postoperative evolution and was discharged without complications 24 days after surgery, with follow-up in the outpatient pediatric surgery clinic.

Figure 4.

DISCUSSION

Despite recent advances, the pathogenesis of congenital diaphragmatic hernia (CDH) remains incompletely understood. Pleuroperitoneal folds (PPFs) are critical in embryonic diaphragm development, acting as temporary structures separating the thoracic and abdominal cavities. These folds contribute to the fibrous tissues of the diaphragmatic muscle and central tendon. Disruptions in PPF myofiber migration, proliferation, or differentiation, or increased apoptosis, may lead to CDH formation [1].

CDH has an incidence of approximately 1.4 per 10,000 pregnancies. The defect is primarily posterolateral (Bochdalek hernia, 70%), less frequently anterior (Morgagni hernia, 27%), or central (2%). Bochdalek hernias predominantly occur on the left side (85%), with right-sided (13%) or bilateral (2%) cases being less common [5].

During embryonic development, abdominal organ herniation into the thoracic cavity can cause pulmonary hypoplasia and other complications, resulting in a neonatal mortality rate of approximately 30%, even in specialized centers with standardized protocols [5].

Prenatal CDH diagnosis is typically achieved via second-trimester ultrasound. Referral to tertiary perinatal centers is essential for optimal management. As 40% of patients have

associated anomalies, genetic testing and advanced imaging are critical for personalized prognosis.

The presence of abdominal organs in the thoracic cavity causes lung compression and mediastinal displacement, potentially leading to pulmonary hypoplasia and hypertension, depending on the defect's size and impact on thoracic structures [6].

Newborns with CDH often face cardiorespiratory adaptation challenges at birth, complicating neonatal resuscitation. Avoiding bag-mask ventilation and opting for immediate endotracheal intubation minimizes barotrauma risk.

Recent diagnostic advances have significantly improved survival rates, reaching 60–70% depending on defect severity and medical/surgical advancements. Later CDH diagnosis (after 25 weeks' gestation) is associated with higher survival but worse pulmonary complications. The lung-to-head ratio (LHR) at 32–33 weeks' gestation helps estimate fetal viability [7].

Intrauterine treatments may enhance lung development, but open fetal surgery is not currently feasible for cases involving liver herniation. Therapeutic approaches promoting lung growth, such as preventing lung fluid egress to increase airway pressure, stimulate cell proliferation, bladder expansion, and pulmonary vascular development.

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Standardized management in tertiary centers achieves a 73% survival rate [7,8,9].

Newborns with CHD often face challenges in cardiorespiratory adaptation at birth, leading to difficulties with neonatal resuscitation. At the time of umbilical cord clamping, they typically exhibit cyanosis and bradycardia. Infants with CHD who have early respiratory distress should be intubated at delivery (whenever possible). Avoid bag-mask ventilation, and instead use a T-piece with the ventilator set to achieve a peak inspiratory pressure below 25 cmH₂O [10].

The successful management of CHD requires a multidisciplinary approach with coordination among specialists in neonatology, pediatric surgery, cardiology, and radiology. When applicable, prompt referral to a tertiary hospital with expertise in CHD management ensures that the newborn receives optimal care, which is crucial for reducing mortality and morbidity rates [11,12,13,14].

In this case, the patient had a prenatal diagnosis of probable duodenal atresia, so CDH management was not pre-planned. After birth, ventilatory deterioration prompted one cycle of positive pressure ventilation, followed by advanced airway management due to persistent respiratory distress. Initial physical findings suggested pneumothorax, but a chest X-ray confirmed CDH. Positive pressure ventilation can exacerbate lung distension and increase barotrauma/volutrauma risk, particularly with high inspiratory pressures or large tidal volumes. Fortunately, no complications arose, and the availability of neonatology, pediatric cardiology, and pediatric surgery enabled comprehensive management. Despite the extensive anatomical defect, the patient's outcome was favorable, with discharge after 24 days and outpatient follow-up, underscoring the importance of prenatal diagnosis and coordinated care in capable facilities to avoid complications [15].

CONCLUSION

Congenital diaphragmatic hernia (CDH) is a severe clinical condition associated with significant morbidity and mortality. However, adequate prenatal monitoring is a critical tool for timely diagnosis and planning comprehensive management. CDH is often detected early in pregnancy via high-resolution prenatal ultrasounds, enabling accurate diagnosis for parents and the design of personalized therapeutic plans with a multidisciplinary approach.

Prenatal diagnosis facilitates anticipation and management of common complications, such as pulmonary hypoplasia and persistent pulmonary hypertension, enabling early formation of specialized teams and delivery planning in centers with neonatal intensive care units, advanced ventilatory support, and specialized surgical services.

Early diagnosis also allows comprehensive counseling for families regarding prognosis and therapeutic options, strengthening the physician-patient relationship and supporting informed, shared decision-making.

In this context, high-quality prenatal care focused on early CDH detection is associated with higher survival rates and improved neonatal quality of life, while optimizing healthcare resource use through timely referral to specialized centers.

Thus, healthcare systems must promote and implement strategies ensuring equitable access to advanced diagnostic technologies and specialized care for high-risk pregnancies, benefiting both expectant mothers and newborns.

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